

THERMOCHROMIC EFFECT AND ADHESION PARAMETERS OF LIQUID CRYSTAL-BASED PRINTING INK ON RECYCLED PRINTING SUBSTRATES

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Abstract: *The application of smart packaging in the fast-developing area of the products with added value has become an attractive field for science and industry. Considering the ecological and market requirements, new smart packaging products should possess both functionality and ecological features. In this research, thermochromic liquid crystal-based printing ink (TLC) was applied on the recycled black uncoated papers using screen printing, as well as on the pre-printed 100% recycled papers. The aim of the research was to analyze the thermochromic effect of the TLC printing ink on the recycled substrates and to analyze the adhesion parameters between all surfaces in the system. In addition, black flexographic printing ink was printed on non-black papers to enable the optimal thermochromic effect after TLC printing ink was screen printed. The adhesion parameters between papers, black flexographic printing ink, and TLC printing ink were calculated and analyzed. To evaluate the thermochromic effect of TLC printing ink, temperature dependent spectral reflectance was measured on all samples and colorimetric values were calculated. The results of the research provided the recommendation on applicability of certain non-black recycled papers as substrates for the thermochromic print after pre-printing with black flexographic printing ink.*

Keywords: thermochromic liquid crystal-based printing ink, smart packaging, adhesion parameters, recycled paper

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermochromic liquid crystal-based (TLC) printing inks change color as a response to surrounding temperature. The color change of TLC printing inks

occurs inside the microcapsules containing thermo-responsive material (Seeboth et al., 2007). The change starts at the defined activation temperature (T_A), occurring in several degrees wide region above the T_A where the color changes throughout the whole visible spectrum from red, orange, yellow, green, blue to violet, the effect known as "color play" (Bamfield, 2010). Inside the color activation region, also named "the color play interval", the color change is caused by reorientation of the molecules in the liquid crystal structure with change in temperature, and the effect this has on the incident light (Christie and Bryant, 2005; "Liquid Crystal Formulations (LCs)," n.d.). TLC inks are best known as temperature indicators, especially for packaging, security printing and brand protection (Sage, 2011; Seeboth et al., 2008). The presented research includes TLC water-based ink printed on three types of recycled papers, and one pressure sensitive (self-adhesive) alternative fiber material. The combination of these materials could be used in development of sustainable applications, in the areas of functional packaging, security printing, etc. Such applications could influence the environment to a lesser extent than conventional materials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this research, TLC printing ink was applied on recycled black uncoated paper (UT) and black alternative fibre paper (CB), and on two types of non-black 100% recycled papers (LG and LTR) which were pre-printed with black flexographic UV-curable printing ink (BL (LG) and BL (LTR)). TLC ink used in this research had water-based formulation (Printcolor, Switzerland). The flexographic printing process was performed in laboratory by means of IGT Printability Tester F1 (IGT Testing Systems, Netherlands). For the purpose of TLC ink printing, a screen printing plate with a mesh density of 43 lines cm^{-1} was prepared. Roughness parameter, R_a (arithmetic mean deviation of the profile) of papers was measured using MarSurf PS 10 (Mahr GmbH, Germany) with stylus method. Surface free energy (SFE) and contact angles on samples were analyzed using the Data Physics OCA 30 goniometer (DataPhysics Instruments GmbH, Germany) and OWRK method (Owens and Wendt, 1969). From the obtained SFE, adhesion parameters (surface free energy of the interphase (γ_{12}), work of adhesion (W_{12}) and wetting coefficient (S_{12}) were calculated (Petković et al., 2019). Temperature-dependent optical properties of TLC prints were measured in a temperature range from 20°C to 47°C, using fiber-based USB 2000+ portable spectrometer (Ocean Optics, USA) SpectraSuite software by Ocean Optics was used to calculate the CIELAB L^* , a^* , b^* values, using D50/2° settings. The printed samples were temperature controlled using the surface

of a water block (EK Water Blocks; EKWB d.o.o., Slovenia) (Jakovljević et al., 2017; Kulčar et al., 2010).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. presents the results of measured roughness parameter R_a . It is visible that CB paper has the roughest surface, and that the lowest roughness was measured on UT paper. One can see that pre-printed black ink causes small changes in surface roughness.

Table 1: R_a roughness parameter measured on paper substrates.

Samples	R_a (μm)	SD
UT	2.392	0.168
CB	6.940	0.693
LG	2.711	0.096
BL (LG)	2.870	0.279
LTR	2.433	0.131
BL (LTR)	2.333	0.117

Results of the surface free energy (SFE) calculations are presented in Figure 1. It is visible that all four unprinted papers have a dominant dispersive component of SFE, with CB paper having the most expressed polar component of SFE among them. When TLC printing ink was printed on the black papers dyed in mass (Figure 1a), the polarity of the new surface (and therefore the polar and total SFE) increased.

Figure 1: Surface free energy components of papers and printed ink layers for a) UT and CB papers, b) pre-printed recycled papers (BL (LG) and BL (LTR)).

Higher polarity of TLC ink when printed directly on black papers dyed in mass indicates that there are different interactions between the black paper surface

and TLC printing ink, than between UV-curable flexographic ink and TLC ink (Figure 1b). Therefore, adhesion parameters are of importance for the assessment of the interactions between the papers and printed layers utilized in this research. Results of the calculated adhesion parameters are presented in Table 2. When assessing the strength of the interaction, all three parameters should be considered – work of adhesion (W_{12}) should be as high as possible, interfacial tension (γ_{12}) should be close to zero, and wetting coefficient (S_{12}) should be positive or equal to zero.

Table 2: Adhesion parameters between papers and printed ink layers

Surfaces in interaction	Adhesion parameters (mN/m)		
	γ_{12}	W_{12}	S_{12}
UT-TLC	12.88	77.72	2.30
CB-TLC	13.10	93.96	-1.76
LG-BL	1.26	83.98	9.06
BL (LG) - TLC	3.63	92.43	-3.13
LTR - BL	4.20	95.08	-5.54
BL (LTR) - TLC	6.79	89.48	-8.46

When observing all three adhesion parameters as a set of values for the interactions including the TLC ink layer, it can be concluded that the adhesion of TLC ink on UT paper was satisfactory in terms of the low S_{12} value, but W_{12} – work that is necessary to separate two layers – is lower than for the rest of the samples where TLC ink is in the interaction with the layer underneath. Furthermore, γ_{12} , which should be minimal, has the highest values when TLC ink is printed directly on the black papers dyed in mass (UT and CB). On the other hand, W_{12} and γ_{12} are more favorable between the layers of TLC ink and pre-printed UV-curable black ink, but S_{12} has a negative value.

Figure 2: CIELAB colour values of the TLC ink printed on UT, LTR, LG and CB printing substrates, presented in (a^* , b^*) (a) and L^*/T diagram (b)

It can be concluded that the best adhesion was achieved between pre-printed LG paper and TLC ink, alongside CB paper and TLC ink. Pre-printed LTR paper should not be recommended as the substrate for the thermochromic print, since S_{12} had a negative value (-8.46), which pointed to the incomplete wetting.

The data obtained from spectral reflection measurements was used in CIELAB colour space, for (a^*, b^*) plot (Figure 2a). The colour play effect results in full loop for all four samples. Differences of the measured samples shown in (a^*, b^*) plot are the result of different properties of the printing substrates, indicated with different size and intensity of the colour loop. The colour play effect is the strongest for the CB sample, which could occur because of the high degree of selective reflection from the structure of the TLC, probably caused by completely black produced paper (dyed in mass). The weakest colour play effect is occurred on LTR and LG samples with printed under-layer. UT sample showed a stronger color play effect than LTR and LG, specifically in red and yellow part of the spectrum, and to a lesser extent, in blue part. The results of the strongest colour play effect measured on CB paper could be the consequence of the surface roughness, which is mostly expressed on CB paper. One can conclude that topography and structure of the substrate have a significant effect on the colour play effect. Results shown in (a^*, b^*) plot are confirmed in $L^*(T)$ diagram (Figure 2b), where L^* (lightness) was examined in temperature dependence. For each sample, the curve extended from 20 to 47 °C, where the reflection peak appeared in visible part of the spectrum. A single maximum occurred in each $L^*(T)$ curve, where the colour had the highest lightness L^* . $L^*(T)$ reached the peak at the temperature of 27 °C for UT sample, at 27.5 °C for CB sample, at 25 °C for LG sample, and for LTR the peak was both at 24.5 and 25 °C. These differences in $T(L^*_{max})$ (°C) are most probably caused by the thickness of printing substrates. CB sample shows the highest intensity, followed by UT, LG and LTR samples.

4 CONCLUSION

In this research, four types of papers were used as substrates for TLC print: two eco-friendly black papers dyed in mass, and two 100% recycled white papers pre-printed with black flexographic UV-curable printing ink. Surface roughness of substrates, surface free energy of all surface layers and adhesion parameters were measured, calculated and analyzed. Spectral reflection measurements were used to display (a^*, b^*) and $L^*(T)$ diagrams and analyze the colour play effect. The results have shown that highest roughness of the substrate improved the color play effect, which was more expressed on the papers dyed in mass because of the high degree of selective reflection. Most favorable adhesion parameters between the TLC printing ink and the substrate were

achieved on pre-printed LG paper, and on black CB paper dyed in mass. Pre-printed LTR paper could not be recommended as a substrate for TLC printing ink because of the ink's incomplete wetting of the surface. All mentioned parameters should be taken into account for development of sustainable applications, functional packaging or security printing using TLC printing inks.

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